

Application of quinone reactions for the assay of amiodarone and ondansetron in pure and pharmaceutical formulations

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Three simple, sensitive and reproducible visible spectrophotometric methods (A-C) are described for the determination of amiodarone (as hydrochloride, AD) or ondansetron (as hydrochloride, OST) in pure samples and pharmaceutical formulation. Methods A, B and C are based on the formation of charge-transfer complexes between AD or OST and chloranil, chloranilic acid or DDQ with $\lambda_{\max}$ 540, 540 or 455 nm, respectively. Regression analysis of Beer's law plots showed good concentration ranges (20–300, 25–300), (30–300, 15–150) and (15–150, 5–60) $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for (AD, OST) in methods A, B and C, respectively. The applicability of the methods has been examined by analyzing tablets of AD or OST.

Amiodarone (AD, antiarrhythmic drug) is official in I.P.¹ and B.P.², while ondansetron (OST, antiemetic) is official in U.S.P.³. There are very few (OST^{4,5}) or none (AD) visible spectrophotometric methods for the determination of the drugs. This note describes three visible spectrophotometric procedures by exploiting the basic property of tertiary amino group (acyclic, AD; imidazolyl, OST) in drug [radical anion or charge-transfer complex formation with quinones such as chloranil (method A), chloranilic acid (method B) and DDQ (method C)].

Results and Discussion

The optimum conditions for the color development of methods were established by varying the parameters one at a time keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the colored species. The conditions so obtained were incorporated in recommended procedures. The optical characteristics are given in Table 1. The additives and excipients that are usually present in tablets do not interfere with the assay of the proposed methods. Comparison of results obtained by proposed and refer-

Table 1. Optical parameters of the proposed methods for AD and OST

Parameter	Method A		Method B		Method C	
	AD	OST	AD	OST	AD	OST
$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	540	540	540	540	455	455
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	20–300	25–300	30–300	15–150	15–150	5–60
Molar absorptivity ($1 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	1.5×10^3	6.49×10^2	9.034×10^2	9.882×10^2	2.13×10^3	3.821×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001$ absorbance unit)	0.430	0.507	0.714	0.333	0.300	8.62×10^{-2}
Regression equation ($Y = a + bc$):						
Slope (b)	2.33×10^{-3}	1.962×10^{-3}	1.4×10^{-3}	2.99×10^{-3}	3.33×10^{-3}	1.162×10^{-2}
Intercept (a)	-6.0×10^{-4}	2.66×10^{-4}	1×10^{-3}	8.66×10^{-4}	-2.66×10^{-4}	-2.0×10^{-4}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999
Relative standard deviation (%) ^a	0.326	0.549	0.666	0.771	0.561	0.446
% Range of error (confidence limits):						
0.05 level	0.342	0.576	0.703	0.810	0.590	0.468
0.01 level	0.536	0.904	1.098	1.27	0.923	0.735
% Error in bulk samples ^b	-0.215	-0.253	0.357	-0.1	-0.300	0.413

^aAverage of six determinations considered. ^bAverage of three determinations.

ence methods for AD or OST in pharmaceutical formulations showed good agreement within $\pm 1.0\%$.

The proposed methods are simple, sensitive and selective and can be used in the routine determination of AD or OST in pure samples and pharmaceutical formulations with reasonable precision and accuracy.

Experimental

Milton Roy spectronic 1201 and Systronics 106 spectrophotometers with 1 cm matched quartz cell were used. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used.

All reagents and chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solutions of chloranil (B.D.H.; $4.067 \times 10^{-3} M$), chloranilic acid (SD-fine; $4.785 \times 10^{-3} M$) and DDQ (Otto kemi; $4.405 \times 10^{-3} M$) were prepared in 1,4-dioxan, the mixture of isopropyl alcohol and chloroform in 1 : 4 ratio and dichloromethane, respectively.

AD or OST (bulk sample or tablet powder equivalent; 100 mg) was treated with 0.1 *N* NaOH solution (20 ml). The free base of the drug was then extracted with chloroform (4×20 ml). The combined chloroform extract was dried with anhyd. sodium sulfate and made upto 100 ml with chloroform to obtain 1 mg ml⁻¹ stock solution. The stock solution was diluted with chloroform to obtain the working standard solution of concentrations for AD (500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, method C) or OST (500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, method B; 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, method C). The stock solution (1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was used directly in methods A and B of AD or method A of OST.

Method A : Into a series of 10 ml calibrated tubes containing aliquots of standard drug solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for AD or OST), 2.0 ml ($4.067 \times 10^{-3} M$) of chloranil was added and the volume in each tube was made upto the mark with DMF. The tubes were heated for 15 min at 65° and were allowed to cool. The absorbance of the

colored species were measured after 30 min at 540 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of drug was deduced from its calibration graph.

Method B : Into a series of 10 ml calibrated tubes containing aliquots of standard drug solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for AD or 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for OST), 2.0 ml ($4.785 \times 10^{-3} M$) of chloranilic acid was added and set aside for 30 min at room temperature. The volume in each tube was made up to mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the colored species was measured at 540 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of drug was deduced from its calibration graph.

Method C : Into a series of 10 ml calibrated tubes containing aliquots of drug solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 500 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for AD or 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for OST), 2.0 ml ($4.405 \times 10^{-3} M$) of DDQ was added and the volume was made upto the mark with dichloromethane. The absorbance was measured after 20 min at 455 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of drug was deduced from its calibration graph.

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